

Organizational values and its relevance in the performances of healthcare sector

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ABSTRACT

Values are the conceptual framework of an organization. It reveals the intentions, directions, and structures of services to be given for the customers. An organization cannot be connected with the customers / community unless it has not been defined with values especially in healthcare sector. The performances of healthcare sector are complex in nature due to the combination features of various services like medical, administrative, technical, supportive and human relations for meeting physical and mental wellbeing of customers. As the field of dependence increases, the complexity of interaction also increases. The combined efforts in services have to be coordinated very well in association with values; otherwise, the relevance of organizational values will be affected with the performances, which will lead to customer dissatisfaction. This study rationally reviews and analyses such scenarios in the healthcare sector. Several strategic/ technological platforms are used in healthcare sector for supporting various dimensions of activities. The major challenge is the identification of suitable platform in relation with the values of the organization. Balanced score card is used to quantify the values and these values are used to analyse the association with performance measures.

INTRODUCTION

In the past, health was treated as a material aspect of life; but among the conditions of the health, mental well-being was not included. Deviations from material aspects were considered as disease and those having such conditions were termed as patients. The word patient is derived from the Latin word 'pati' which means capable of bearing affliction with calmness and capable of bearing delay for the right moment. During that period, sources of treatments were very minimal, so that the demand for getting treatment was proportionally high. Patients were willing to bear at any extent to meet their stated need - to get the treatment. Now the situations are changed. There are many sources of treatment facilities available at the tip of fingers with distinctive speciality. The characteristic of patient is replaced by the characteristic of customer. Customer can demand for services at any time. The needs of the customers and its patterns are changed. In addition to the basic need of getting the treatment, they have started for demanding subsidiary services too. The trends in healthcare sector have been changing followed by these varying service demands of customers. Since more options are available with customers, organizations are forced to ensure their sustainability by transforming themselves as the focal point of attraction in the service delivery with the support of various technologies. As the first step of transformation, organization has to declare its uniqueness in the provision of services by narrating what they have to give the customers as good as it can be. The values inculcated by the organization will be the core of such declared statement. The values of an organization determine the degree of facilities and provisions needed to the customers for meeting their needs. Hence all activities, including optimization of activities using technological platform, should be in consensus with values of the organization.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The uniqueness of an organization is its values. Values can attract right customers. People are choosing one organization over the another due to the values followed by the organizations. Values can give directions to meet the objectives. Hence organizational values have the relevance in coordinating the services as well as the usage of resources. Same values may be there in different organizations, but providing optimum services in consensus with the values officiates the 'value identity' of that organization. In an organization, the way people think of their activities in relation with organizational values reveals how much they are aligned with the organization rather than considering their job as the means of financial gaining. Value prioritizes the content of services in which it is offering. Hence all the means leading towards the priorities of the customers have to be studied.

The healthcare system is a collective form of skilled and unskilled people with structured association of various entities such as clinical, administrative and supportive departments for providing preventive, curative and rehabilitative services to the needy population in the community so as to make them physically and mentally sound. When a customer receives services from a healthcare provider, generally there arise two types of needs - stated need and

implied needs, based upon the severity, dependence, financial status and priority concern. The actual need of a patient is called the stated need and those subsidiary needs are called implied needs. The actual need may be a specific one (for example to get the service of a particular consultant), but the implied needs may be trivial many (amenities and comfort requirements). The term 'trivial' indicates that priorities are changed between the customers. The stated and implied needs to be facilitated as per the requirement of the customers; otherwise, customers will not be satisfied. The healthcare organization is a combination of various entities (registration, medical records, diagnostic services, therapeutic services, internal transportation etc) but the objectives of each entity are different, moreover, their movements are at no-linear manner to meet the objectives. Even though each entity has different objectives, the ultimate aim of all entities is the customer satisfaction by making good performances. For this, prioritization of the needs of the customers at each service point to be identified and those services to be provided to the customers accordingly. As the number of customers for receiving the service are very high, the said activities cannot be done manually. Hence it is needed a strategic / technological platform for catching, computing, connecting, combining, accelerating, interfacing and processing the proposed activities. For identifying the prioritization of the content of the services as per the values, it is required to study the facilities available for the performance of the organization such as automations in services, automation gaps in services, humanizing touch required in services etc.

IMPLEMENTATION AND METHODS

Most of the organizations have failed to identify the causative and responsive features behind the technological platform. They were not able to relate the practices in the technological platform and the values followed by the organizations. Such pitfalls are able to make distributive failures in values within the system.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Organizational values

Organizational values are the extensive form of human values. It acts as a pivotal point for attracting the customers and helps to hold-back the customers along with the organization by making an intangible relationship. Organizational values can make creative energy between internal (staff) and external (patients and stakeholders) customers and it gives the threshold to move forward with the intentions and commitment of the organization. In the past, it was assumed that organizational values are under the purview of intangibility. Later studies reveal that organizational values are tangible concept and it can be monitored and measured, as mentioned by [1] Musek Lešnik. An organization's ability to successfully adopt any particular core value is a function of its existing capabilities.

Organizational values have significant role in organizational structure [2] Walsh et al. 1981, Kabanoff et al. 1995), organizational culture [3] Pettigrew,

1979) (Adhocracy Culture, Clan Culture, Hierarchy Culture, and Market Culture - [4] Quinn & Kim Cameron), organizational identity [5] Ashforth & Mael, 1989), organizational strategy [6] Bansal, 2003) and organizational means. Organizational structure details the privileges of activities, organizational culture details how things are doing, organizational identity details who we are, organizational strategy details the mode of achieving competitive advantages and organizational means details the way of achieving the goals. All these characteristics have tangible relationship with operational activities and the results. Any changes in the said roles can lead to distributive changes within the system. For ensuring the easiness of operational activities, several technological changes are regularly adopting in healthcare organizations. Hence conscious execution of strategies with adequate changes to be considered for maintaining the organizational values as such.

Performance of an organization

Performance is a situation 'conditioned with responses and tasks' for achieving specific goals or results. According to [7] Skinner 1957, what did people leave after a behaviour is called results. It reveals that behaviour has more significance on results, hence organizational behaviour has an impact on its performances. The behaviour of an organization depends upon the values it holds. As said earlier, core values of an organization determine its existing capabilities. In order to maintain those capabilities, adequate resources are required. The main resources of an organization are man, money, materials and machineries. Normally a resource itself cannot perform an operational activity independently, for example, money itself cannot do anything, materials and machineries itself cannot do any operations; but humanization measures can do the services independently for the customers by using their five senses in various combinations as per the situation demands. It is not possible to measure exactly the worthiness of such human interferences, especially in healthcare sector. Combinations of resources are required on timely basis to perform the activities in an effective manner. Performance of an organization is an inflated behaviour on contingencies to make maximum return from the means of services. Effectiveness and efficiency are the key indicators of performance. Effectiveness is the means (ways) of achievement and efficiency is the desired stages of achievement. As per [8] Robert S Kaplan and David Norton, the values of an organization can be converted as performance measures. If the process improvement of the organization is not in consensus with the values of the organization, the same will be reflected in the performances. Hence any value additions to be done in the existing system should be in consensus with the values of the organization.

Technological platform

Usually, technological platforms are used to take advantages on unfavourable situations or to cover-up unproductive repetitive works. According to the Oxford dictionary, technology is the application of scientific knowledge for meeting practical purposes and it needs an infrastructure platform and mechanical supports to perform as the way it is scientifically programmed. As the healthcare sector is complex in nature, the efforts of each entity to serve the customers have to be coordinated properly to draw the final outcome as well as the customer satisfaction. Moreover, priority needs of the customers to be identified in each stage of services. Manual compilation of all such factors is tedious, hence it is needed a computing platform to healthcare organizations for providing better and uninterrupted services. But the selection of a technological platform is a major concern. The healthcare system is following system-oriented approach. Hence inter-related inter-dependent activities are bounded to support each other and to ensure the continuity of services. In the case of a technological platform, the responsive features associated with it defines how far it makes consecutive changes inwardly and outwardly. The required changes in the system mainly depends upon the organizational structure, organizational culture, organizational identity, organizational strategy, and organizational means, so that it can lead to organizational values too. In order to avoid mismatches in the receptiveness of services, the required changes in the system have to be done in consensus with the values of the organization. Customization is possible to incorporate in all technological platforms. But the customization has certain limitations as the same is a limited version of automation. [9] Bhuvan Unhelkar and Tad Gonsalves states that automation repeat the activities or helps to repeat the activities based on the schedule fixed. Such pre-fixed schedules are termed as customization. Identifying a situation to act accordingly or making sensible decisions based on the available data are not possible with automation. For example, consider the situation of a patient who cannot see a consultant without completing the diagnostic package attached to the automated platform! Here the factors such as - the reports available with the patient, the economic status of the patient, severity condition of the patient, other cross consultation needed for the patient etc are not being considered. The system could have provided more reliable services in association with values, if it has intelligence-based platform rather than automation. If the organization is not taking the support of the technological platforms for providing the services, the society cannot move forward with receptiveness, precision and promptness of services.

Artificial Intelligence & Machine Learning

The intention to mimic the intelligences of human-beings with the support of scientific technologies was a milestone in the world of virtual reality. Human intelligence has the capability to act with suitable formations in various situations or contingencies deprived of violating the personal values. The outcomes (performances) of activities will be at optimum level if the activities are in consensus with their values in any situations. According to Bhuvan Unhelkar, Tad Gonsalves, AI is a non-real senses of intelligences demonstrated

by machineries by performing task with automation, augmentation, manipulation, exploration, evaluation etc but it requires human support to attain the result as planned. In the writings of [10] Hansen & Nelson, it is described that node connectivity, network topology and learning rules are the critical components of Artificial Neural Network. The functioning of these critical components is comparable with Biological Neural Network of human beings. Hence it is possible to code or program a responsive technology to be followed in various situations as doing by human intelligence. For this purpose, it is needed to customize the technological platform and to feed the same with relevant data in consensus with organizational values. According to [11] DonHee Lee 1 and Seong No Yoon, it is possible to reap the benefits of Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning by using it properly especially in, care of patients, identification of clinical risk, practices of management, rational decision making etc. Decisiveness in services can be ensured with process refinement while using these technologies. The services providing through artificial intelligence have to be flexible to meet with contingencies and specific requirements of customers, otherwise it will be same as automated platform. Normally most of the healthcare activities have subjective and objective features. Subjective features of activities are based on personal interpretations but not on facts. In the case of objective features, the fact plays the key role. The flexibility in contingencies by differentiating the subjective and objective needs of the customers in consensus with the values of the organization is the main challenge in the responsive technology involved in artificial intelligence. Most of the subjective features of an activity need humanization approaches at a certain level, especially in healthcare sector. In such cases, automation gap has to be provided by the technology itself to enter human beings for further proceedings of the services. Otherwise, failures or dissatisfaction may happen within the system. According to [12] William B Rouse, there are two types of failures - point failure and distributed failure. Point failures are masked in nature but, it is easily recognizable and evident for readdressing. Distributed failures will not be apparent till the consequences are revealed. The healthcare organization is based on system-oriented approach, hence there are more possibilities to form distributive failures within the system, otherwise, the organization should have control over the technological platform (AI & ML). The selection of a virtual platform by identifying the responsive technology is the determining factor of how it is worthful for the society and the organization in consensus with values.

Performance Optimization

Optimization means equipping a situation or a resource for accomplishing the expected results efficiently in a manner as good as it can be. Performance means an action with specific character while using a resource or behaving with a situation. An action with character for achieving something reveals the means (effectiveness) of achievement. Hence the optimization of performances ensures efficiency and effectiveness of related activities in a system. Optimization of activities depends upon effective coordination of inter-related and inter-dependent activities, but the performances of activities are gravitated on personal and organizational characteristics as well as values. According to [13] Finn Holm, performance optimization is a holistic approach as it is intended to explore all possibilities for meeting the subjective and objective requirements of the customers at any time. Optimization of activities in consensus with organizational values is more authoritative and reliable than achieving the same by compromising with the relevance of specific characters (values) associated with the organization. The customization approaches required to improve the quality of care and to eliminate the unwanted service elements and the cost have to be in align with the values of the organization. In such situations, the services offered have to be flexible with various contingencies. Optimization of services on various contingencies depends upon the following realities- a) the priorities and the depth of services are determined by the combination features of organizational values b) the technological substitutions are happening within the organization irrespective of considering required infrastructural changes c) the frequency of occurrences of unintended situations are varying from organization to organization. For the purpose of performance analysis, all such situations are considered as unfavourable situations. The significance of resource management emanates from such unfavourable situations. In order to make control over the unfavorable situations, the resources have to be utilized at optimum level. It needs logical thinking and coordinated efforts than mere calculations. The study of [14] Dr. Domenico Lepore shows that the optimization of the resources in unfavourable situations can be done through resource levelling, resources smoothing, reverse resources allocating etc. Since healthcare organizations are complex in nature and having system-oriented approach, wrong positioning of any performance indicators can lead to distributive failures in the system. Hence a 'concerted effect' to be considered while optimizing the performances of service organizations - especially in healthcare sector.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

From the above discussed points, it is implicit that organizational values are able to make an impact on the performances of the organization, in fact several studies have proved the same. There are many statistical tools such as Balanced performance measurement matrix by [15] Keegan et al. (1989), Performance Pyramid System by [16] Judson (1990), Balanced scorecard framework by Kaplan and Norton (1992), Performance PRISM by [17] Neely (2002) etc are available in the research field to quantify the values of the

organizations as per the study requirement. Once the values of the organization are categorized under the respective study headings and quantified, its association with the performance of the organization can be measured. For analysing the performance of the organization, standardized tool has to be used. Several strategic platforms are used by organizations for improving the performances of services. The practices followed by the organization in such platforms can be identified separately and studied. So that the association as well as causation between values, performance and practices can be identified. As the values and the practices in the strategic platform are independent on the performances, the selection of a suitable platform in association with the values of the organization can give optimum performances than selecting the same for operational easiness only. All such study proposals reveal that organizational values have more relevance on the performances of organizations.

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